

The Reaction of Arylmagnesium Halides with Succinic Anhydride^ψ

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Manuscript received 8 December 1993

The reaction of equimolar amounts of phenylmagnesium bromide and succinic anhydride in THF at -78° for 2 h gives subsequent to hydrolytic work-up, 3-benzoylpropionic acid in 76% yield and 4,4-diphenyl-4-butyrolactone in 3% yield. When two molar equivalents of the Grignard reagent are employed, the yields of these products are respectively 85 and 14%. On the other hand, when four equivalents of the Grignard reagent are employed for every equivalent of succinic anhydride at 66° , a diketone, 1,4-diphenylbutane-1,4-dione is obtained in 72% yield. Other products include 4,4-diphenyl-4-butyrolactone (19%) and 3-benzoylpropionic acid (6%). Under comparable conditions, 4-methyl- and 4-methoxyphenylmagnesium halides react similarly with succinic anhydride, giving fair yields (49–53%) of the corresponding diketones. However, 4-chlorophenylmagnesium chloride only gives the keto-acid (12%) and lactone (42%), but no diketone.

In connection with our work on the reactions of organocoppermagnesium reagents with cyclic anhydrides of dicarboxylic acids¹, we thought it interesting to study the reactions of the latter with Grignard reagents.

Knight and Pattenden² recently reported the reaction of ethylmagnesium bromide with 2-methylmaleic anhydride (**1**) to produce a mixture of carbinols which on dehydration gave a 3 : 2 mixture of ylidenebut-2-enolides (**2** and **3**). On the other hand, the addition of the same Grignard reagent to 2-phenyl-3-methoxymaleic anhydride (**4**), followed by dehydration of the intermediate carbinol, led to a single ylidenebutenolide (**5**). The use of excess ethylmagnesium bromide resulted in an additional product, 4,4-diethyl-3-methoxy-2-phenylbut-2-enolide (**6**).

In contrast, our work with arylmagnesium halides and succinic anhydride shows that a keto-acid, 3-arylpropionic acid, and a diketone compound, 1,4-diarylbutane-1,4-dione, may be obtained in high yields. The yield of one of

the products may be made to predominate over the other by suitably varying the reaction conditions.

We recently disclosed the preliminary results obtained from the reaction of phenylmagnesium bromide with succinic anhydride³. We have now extended this work to include other arylmagnesium halides, and we report here the details of this work and the work described in the preliminary communication.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the reaction of equimolar amounts of phenylmagnesium bromide with succinic anhydride (**7**) in THF at -78° for 2 h, gives, subsequent to hydrolytic work-up, 3-benzoylpropionic acid (**9**, Ar = Ph) and 4,4-diphenyl-4-butyrolactone (**8**, Ar = Ph) respectively, 76 and 3% yields. Higher reaction temperatures produce synthetically unhelpful mixtures of products. The use of two equivalents of the Grignard reagent for each equivalent of the an-

^ψDedicated to Professor D. P. Chakraborty whose contribution to Chemistry, to the Indian Chemical Society, and whose warm personality act as a source of constant inspiration.

hydride at -78° for 2 h increases the yields of the products **9** (Ar = Ph) is now produced in 85% yield and **8** (Ar = Ph) in 14% yield. Although the yield of the keto-acid is increased by 9% in the latter experiment, it really does not justify the increased cost involved in the use of the large excess of the Grignard reagent.

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF SOME ARYLMAGNESIUM HALIDES WITH SUCCINIC ANHYDRIDE

Ar	n	Temp °C	Yield (%)		
			8 ^b	9 ^c	10 ^d
C ₆ H ₅	1	-78	3	76	—
C ₆ H ₅	2	-78	14	85	—
C ₆ H ₅	2	-5	39	51	—
C ₆ H ₅	2	27	41	34	—
C ₆ H ₅	4	66	19	6	72
4-Me-C ₆ H ₄	4	66	15	16	53
4-MeO-C ₆ H ₄	4	66	15	14	49
4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4	66	42	12	—

^a7 = Succinic anhydride; ^b8 = 4,4-diaryl-4-butyrolactone; ^c9 = 3-arylpropionic acid; ^d10 = 1,4-diarylbutane-1,4-dione

In contrast, the reaction of four equivalents of phenylmagnesium bromide with one equivalent of succinic anhydride in THF at the reflux temperature for 2 h gives, subsequent to hydrolytic work-up, 1,4 diphenylbutane-1,4-dione (**10**) in 72%, the keto-acid **9** (Ar = Ph) in 6% and the lactone, **8** (Ar = Ph) in 19% yield. This is surprising because excess Grignard reagent is expected to react further with the keto group to produce tertiary alcohols. However, under our conditions, this does not appear to happen. To the contrary, it provides an easy route to this useful difunctional compound. Table 1 shows that 4-methyl- and 4-methoxyphenylmagnesium bromides also react with succinic anhydride similarly, giving fair yields (49–53%) of the corresponding 1,4-diketones. However, when 4-chlorophenylmagnesium chloride is employed, no diketone is formed, the main product being the corresponding lactone (42%) and keto-acid (12%). Some chlorobenzene is also formed, presumably from the hydrolysis of the unreacted 4-chlorophenylmagnesium chloride.

We believe that a four-fold excess of the Grignard reagent is needed for the formation of the diketo compounds probably because two equivalents of the Grignard reagent complex with the two carbonyl oxygens of the anhydride during the initial stages of the reaction. These interactions enhance the electron deficiencies of the carbonyl carbons making them more susceptible to the nucleophilic attack by the Grignard reagents. The lack of the diketone formation in the reaction of 4-chlorophenylmagnesium chloride with succinic anhydride, reflects on the reduced nucleophilicity of the chlorophenyl group of the Grignard reagent.

Experimental

The reactions described here were carried out under a positive pressure of oxygen-free, dry nitrogen atmosphere and in dry equipment. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was distilled from sodium-benzophenone ketyl before use. Commercial succinic anhydride was purified by recrystallising it from acetic anhydride by following the published procedure⁴. All the arylmagnesium halides were prepared by published procedures^{5–8}. Nmr spectra were recorded using Varian XL (400 MHz) and Bruker (270 MHz) spectrometers, mass spectra on Finnigan 1020 and A.E.I. MS30 instruments and ir spectra on a Shimadzu 470 spectrophotometer.

Reaction of phenylmagnesium bromide with succinic anhydride. General procedure : Phenylmagnesium bromide (0.02 mol) in THF was cooled to -78° with the help of a dry ice/ethanol bath. Succinic anhydride (0.01 mol) was added to it and the mixture stirred vigorously for 2 h. The mixture was then hydrolysed with approximately 10% HCl (100 cm³) and extracted thrice with ether. The ether extract was further extracted with 5% NaOH solution and the aqueous layer acidified with concentrated HCl. A milky-white colloidal suspension obtained was cooled in a refrigerator overnight when some crystals appeared. The crystals were dried under reduced pressure for several hours and identified as 3-benzoylpropionic acid (85%).

The ether extract that remained after alkali extraction was concentrated and some light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) was added to it. Crystals of 4,4-diphenyl-4-butyrolactone came out as a white solid in 14% yield.

Table 1 gives the details of further variation of this work.

Reaction of arylmagnesium halides with succinic anhydride in THF at 66°: An arylmagnesium halide (0.02 mol) was prepared in THF (50 cm³) following the published procedure. Succinic anhydride (0.005 mol) was added to it at room temperature. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h in an oil bath with constant stirring. The mixture was then cooled in a water-bath, hydrolysed with approximately 10% HCl (100 cm³) and extracted thrice with ether. The ether extract was further extracted with 5% NaOH solution, the aqueous layer acidified with concentrated HCl and again extracted with ether. Ether was evaporated and the semi-solid obtained was recrystallised from hot water to give 3-aryloxypropionic acid.

The water-insoluble semi-solid was recrystallised from absolute alcohol to give (i) 1,4-diaryl-1,4-butanedione and (ii) crude 4,4-diaryl-4-butyrolactone which was then recrystallised from light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°). The solid obtained after removal of ether from the ether extract that remained after alkali extraction, was recrystallised from absolute alcohol to give a further crop of 1,4-diaryl-1,4-butanedione.

3-Benzoylpropionic acid: White flaky solid, m.p. 115–16° (lit.⁹ 116°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 2 900–3 500 (OH), 1 710 (C=O), 1 590, 1 350, 1 240, 770, 690 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS) 2.77 (2H, t, CH₂), 3.27 (2H, t, CH₂), 7.10–7.93 (5H, m, ArH), 8.27 (1H, s, OH, exchangeable with D₂O); m/z 178 (M)⁺, 161 (M-OH)⁺, 160 (M-H₂O)⁺, 105 (C₆H₅CO)⁺, 77 (C₆H₅)⁺, 51 (C₄H₃)⁺.

4,4-Diphenyl-4-butyrolactone: White solid, m.p. 90–91° (lit.¹⁰ 90.5–91.5°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 780

(C=O), 1 450 (aromatic skeletal vibration), 900–1 225, 760 and 710 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ 2.57 (2H, t, CH₂-CO), 2.9 (2H, t, CH₂-CO), 7.25–7.47 (10H, m, ArH); m/z 238 (M)⁺, 194 (M-CO₂)⁺, 181 (C₆H₄COC₆H₅)⁺, 161 (M-C₆H₅)⁺, 105 (C₆H₅-CO)⁺, 77 (C₆H₅)⁺, 51 (C₄H₃)⁺.

1,4-Diphenyl-1,4-butanedione: White solid (72%), m.p. 144–45° (lit.¹¹ 143–45°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 680 (C=O), 1 600, 1 460, 1 380, 1 230, 1 000, 740, 700 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS) 3.36 (4H, s, CH₂CH₂), 7.167–8.067 (5H, m, ArH); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS) 32.61 (CH₂), 128.2 (*ortho* C), 133.2 (*meta* C), 136.8 (*para* C) and 196.7 ppm (CO); m/z 298 (M)⁺, 133 (M-CO-C₆H₅)⁺, 105 (CO-C₆H₅)⁺, 77 (C₆H₅)⁺.

1,4-Bis(4-methylphenyl)-1,4-butanedione: White shiny solid (53%) m.p. 158.8–59.5, (lit.¹² 158–60°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 670 (C=O), 1 600, 1 460, 1 400, 1 370 1 172, 1 010, 778 cm⁻¹; ¹nmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS) 2.44 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.44 (4H, s, CH₂CH₂), 7.28 (4H, d, ArH), 7.96 (4H, d, ArH); m/z 266 (M)⁺, 147 (M-CO-C₆H₄-CH₃)⁺, 119 (CO-C₆H₄-CH₃)⁺, 91 (C₆H₄-CH₃)⁺.

3-(4-Methylbenzoyl)propionic acid: White flaky solid, m.p. 126–27° (lit.¹³ 127–28°); ν_{\max} (nujol)

2 900–3 500 (OH), 1 680–1 700 (C=O), 1 610, 1 470, 1 380, 1 230, 1 180, 810, 680 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 2.40 (1H, s, CH_3), 2.77 (2H, t, CH_2), 3.27 (2H, t, CH_2), 7.00–7.90 (5H, m, ArH), 9.84 (1H, s, OH, exchangeable with D_2O); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 21.65 (CH_3), 28.15 (CH_2), 33.06 (CH_2), 128.2 (*meta* C), 129.3 (*ortho* C), 133.9 (*para* C), 144.2 (*tertiary* C), 179.1 (C=O), 197.6 ppm (C=O); m/z 192 (M^+) 19%, 175 ($M\text{-OH}^+$) 3.5%, 119 ($\text{CO-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-CH}_3^+$) 100%, 91 ($\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-CH}_3^+$) 59%, 65 (C_5H_5^+), 51 (C_4H_3^+) 3%, 45 (COOH^+) 3%.

4,4-Bis(4-methylphenyl)-4-butyrolactone : White solid, m.p. 47–48°; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 030 (aromatic CH), 2 950, 2 910 and 2 850 (aliphatic CH), 1 775 (C=O), 1 600, 1 500, 1 445, 1 410, 1 290, 1 225, 1 210, 1 160, 1 050, 980, 910, 820, 800, 780, 735 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 2.298 (6H, s, CH_3), 2.545 (2H, t, J 5.9 Hz, CH_2), 2.842 (2H, t, J 5.9 Hz, CH_2), 7.130 (4H, d, *ortho* H), 7.278 (4H, d, *meta* H); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 20.91 (CH_3), 29.09 (C^3H_2), 34.96 (C^2H_2) and 89.78 (*tertiary* C^4), 125.2 (*meta* C^7), 129.1 (*ortho* C^6), 137.5 (*para* C^8), 140.2 (*quaternary* C^5), 176.3 (C=O); m/z 266 (M^+) 37%, 211 [$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3)_2\text{COH}^+$] 65%, 175 ($M\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3^+$) 27%, 119 ($\text{COC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3^+$) 100%, 105 ($\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{CH}_3^+$) 17%, 91 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3^+$) 83%, 77 (C_6H_5^+) 9%, 65 (C_5H_5^+) 58%, 55 (CHCH_2CO^+) 31%, 51 (C_4H_3^+) 21%.

1,4-Bis(4-methoxyphenyl)-1,4-butanedione: White solid (49%) m.p. 154–55° (lit.¹⁴ 154°); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 670 (C=O), 1 600, 1 465, 1 375, 1 180, 990 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 3.40 (4H,

s, CH_2CH_2), 3.88 (6H, s, OCH_3), 6.94 (4H, d, ArH), 8.02 (4H, d, ArH); m/z 298 (M^+) 163 ($M\text{-CO-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3^+$), 135 ($\text{CO-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3^+$), 107 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3^+$), 77 (C_6H_5^+).

3-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)propionic acid : White flaky solid, m.p. 146–147° (lit.¹⁵ 146–47°); ν_{max} (nujol) 2 900–3 500 (OH), 1 680–1 700 (C=O), 1 610, 1 470, 1 380, 1 230, 1 180, 810, 680 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 2.40 (1H, s, CH_3), 2.77 (2H, t, CH_2), 3.27 (2H, t, CH_2), 7.00–7.90 (5H, m, ArH), 9.84 (1H, s, OH, exchangeable with D_2O); m/z 208 (M^+) 32%, 191 ($M\text{-OH}^+$) 19%, 163 ($M\text{-COOH}^+$) 3%, 135 ($\text{CO-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OCH}_3^+$) 100%, 107 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-OCH}_3^+$) 17%, 92 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}^+$) 18%, 77 (C_6H_5^+) 26%, 65 (C_5H_5^+) 9%, 55 ($\text{CH-CH}_2\text{-CO}^+$) 3.5%, 45 (COOH^+) 3%.

4,4-Bis(methoxyphenyl)-4-butyrolactone : White solid, m.p. 108–09° (lit.¹⁴ 107.5–08.5°); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 050 (aromatic CH), 2 950, 2 910 and 2 850 (aliphatic CH), 1765 (C=O), 1600, 1500, 1445, 1 365, 1 295, 1 255, 1 180, 1 165, 1 030, 980, 910, 840 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 2.566 (2H, t, CH_2), 2.829 (2H, t, CH_2), 3.778 (6H, s, OCH_3), 6.849 (4H, d, *meta* H), 7.289 (4H, d, *ortho* H); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3 , TMS) 29.31 (CH_2), 35.61 (CH_2), 55.28 (OCH_3), 89.69 (*quaternary* C), 113.6 (*meta* C), 126.6 (*ortho* C), 135.3 (*ipso* C), 156.1 (*para* C), 176.3 ppm (C=O). Mass spectral data are presented in Table 2.

3-(4-Chlorobenzoyl)propionic acid : White shiny flaky solid, m.p. 130–31° (lit.¹³ 130–31.5°); ν_{max}

TABLE 2—MASS SPECTRAL DATA

<i>m/z</i>	Ion	Formula
298	M^+	 Ans = C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃
267	[M-OMe] ⁺	 A
253	[M-HCO ₂] ⁺	
243	[M-C ₃ H ₃ O] ⁺	(Ans) ₂ C=O ⁺ -H
223	[A-HCO ₂] ⁺	
191	[M-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ -4] ⁺	
135 (base peak)	[4-CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄ -C=O] ⁺	
121	[C ₇ H ₆ (OCH ₃)] ⁺	
107	(4-CH ₃ -O-C ₆ H ₄) ⁺	
92	(C ₆ H ₄ -O) ⁺	
77	(C ₆ H ₅) ⁺	
56	H ₂ C-CH ₂ -C=O ⁺	

175.3 (C=O); *m/z* 308 (central peak) (M^+) 21% [with correct isotope pattern for two chlorine atoms], 271 ($M\text{Cl}$)⁺ 13% [correct isotope pattern for one Cl], 251 ($M\text{-C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}$)⁺ 91% [correct isotope pattern for two Cl], 195 ($M\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$)⁺ 25% [correct isotope pattern for one Cl], 139 ($M\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl, -CO}$)⁺ 100% [isotope pattern for one Cl], 111 (C₆H₄Cl)⁺ 67%, 75 (C₆H₃)⁺ 92%, 55 (CHCH₂CO)⁺ 100%.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the International Program in Chemical Sciences, University of Uppsala, Sweden, and to the University Grants Commission, Bangladesh, for financial help. The facilities of library work provided at the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, are gratefully appreciated.

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(nujol) 2 900–3 400 (OH), 1 680–1 690 (C=O), 1 590, 1 460 1 400, 1 380, 1 230, 1 180, 1 100, 820, 760, 730 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS), 2.90 (1H, t, CH₂), 3.37 (2H, t, CH₂), 7.20–8.23 (5H, m, ArH), 9.77 (1H, s, OH); *m/z* 212 (M^+) 30% [with correct isotpoe pattern for one chlorine atom], 195 ($M\text{-OH}$)⁺ 59.5% [with correct isotope pattern for one chlorine atom], 111 (C₆H₄Cl)⁺ 72% [correct isotope pattern of one chlorine atom], 75 (C₆H₃)⁺ 37%, 55 (CH-CH₂CO)⁺ 7.5%, 45 (COOH)⁺ 7%.

4,4-Bis(4-chlorophenyl)-4-butyrolactone : White solid, m.p. 124.5–125.6; ν_{max} (nujol) 1765 (C=O), 1 455, 1 225, 900, 760, 720 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS) 2.588 (2H, t, CH₂), 2.860 (2H, t, CH₂), 7.310 (8H, m, ArH); ¹³C nmr δ (CDCl₃, TMS) 28.86 (C³H₂), 35.51 (C²H₂), 88.70 (tertiary C⁴), 126.7 (*meta* C⁷), 128.9 (C⁶ *ortho*), 134.2 (C⁸ *para*), 141.1 (quaternary C⁵),

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